

ISic1064

I.Sicily inscription 1064

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2016.06.27 (Prag)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mutyca

Place of origin (modern)

Modica

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 34

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140544

1. Ἀντώνι-

2. ος Εὐπρα-

3. κτος ἐνθά-

4. δε κίτε· ἐτε-

5. λεύτησεν

6. μηνὶ Ἰουνίῳ

7. ἀπὸ κα(λανδῶν) κε'

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492691

EDCS 39102219

PHI 140544

Bibliography

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